

PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

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A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“BALANCING LIFE’S LEDGER: LEARNING IS UNENDING”

Ledgers and lessons have guided my days,
Each number and challenge shaped my ways.

Amid life’s accounts of loss and gain,
Resilience grew from struggle and pain.

Never deterred by hardship or test,
I balanced my goals, gave every quest my best.

Nicefore I. Dua—my father, my guide—
Gave me the courage that numbers can’t hide.

I found my purpose in learning’s art,
Sharing knowledge with an open heart.

Understanding figures, yet teaching with soul,
Nurturing minds has become my goal.

Education and ethics walk hand in hand,
Never forgetting where I first began.

Driven to serve, to teach, to refine,
I reconcile life’s balance sheet line by line.

Numbers and people, both worth defending—
Gratitude reminds me: learning is unending.